

Enhancing Educational Decision-Making: An Ensemble Approach to Course Recommendation

Febin Vinod

PG Scholar

Master of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirappally, India
febinvinod2024@mca.ajce.in

Jetty Benjamin

Assistant Professor

Master of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirappally, India
jettybenjamin@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract— In the field of guidance and course recommendations, achieving personalized suggestions has always faced challenges. Factors, like data and the need for perspectives in decision making have been obstacles. However recent advancements in machine learning have brought about an approach called Ensemble Learning in Course Recommendation. This method combines machine learning models to offer enhanced course recommendations. In our research we introduce the ELCR framework, which leverages the strengths of models and utilizes majority voting to provide recommendations. Taking inspiration from applications of Ensemble Learning in domains we carefully select and train three classifiers; XGBoost, K Nearest Neighbors and Support Vector Machine. These classifiers capture aspects like student preferences, academic performance and other relevant factors. We then create a model that combines their predictions using a majority voting approach. Overall Ensemble Learning in Course Recommendation shows promise in improving decision making by catering to a range of student preferences and needs. Our findings indicate that better academic guidance can have effects, on both students and educational institutions.

Keywords— Educational Guidance, Course Recommendation, Ensemble Learning, Machine Learning Models, XGBoost, K-Nearest Neighbors, Support Vector Machine, Majority Voting, Academic Decision-Making.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the rapidly evolving educational landscape, informed decisions about what courses should be offered for students' learning and professional development are of utmost importance. This task is often challenging, as it requires nuanced understandings of individual requirements, academic backgrounds and career aspirations. To address this issue, we developed a course recommendation system that leverages the power of machine learning to provide tailored guidance for students exploring their best educational options.

The Challenge

Even high school graduates and experienced professionals are faced with an impressive array of courses, each with its own unique needs, content, and potential career outcomes and the most appropriate course choice from a great diet this is a difficult task. Additionally, as educators and organizations continue to improve their programs, they often introduce new courses and specializations. The result is an ever-growing learning environment that can leave students feeling lost in a sea of possibilities.

Our Approach

To address these challenges, we developed a recommendation framework that leverages the capabilities of three different machine learning models, each with its own strengths and weaknesses. These models include XGBoost classification, K-Nearest Neighbors classification, and Support Vector Machine classification. This classification analyzes and interprets a variety of factors, such as adding two credits in English, Mathematics, Science, Commerce, Humanities, High School CGPA and StreamPoint, to provide individual learning recommendations.

Ensemble Learning

What makes our approach unique is the use of ensemble learning, where these individual observations come together to provide consensus recommendations. Through the majority voting method, the cluster model combines the insights from each category to provide robust and accurate study recommendations. The ultimate goal is to help students make informed decisions that consider multiple aspects of their academic background and aspirations.

Beyond Courses: A Holistic Approach

Our framework goes beyond curriculum recommendation by considering the entire educational experience. We also provide insights into the top five colleges offering recommended courses, provided by the National Institutional Ranking Framework (NIRF) for 2023[5]. This adds further guidance, helping students make decisions with their learning objectives match their aspirations.

In this paper, we present the architecture, methodology, and practical application of our trained model. By taking a data-driven approach, we aim to empower students and staff with the information they need to successfully navigate the complex educational landscape. Our model is designed not only to compliment learning but also to facilitate a successful and satisfying educational journey.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

A. Course Recommendation System Using Machine Learning.

This paper[1] focuses on a course recommendation system based on machine learning techniques such as collaborative filtering and content-based filtering.

B. Hybrid Approach for Course Recommendation System Based on User and Item Profiles.

In this paper[2] the authors present a hybrid approach for course recommendation, considering both user and item profiles. This system that combines content-based filtering and collaborative filtering techniques.

C. Course Recommendation System using Deep Learning” by Shonal Vaz, Sushama Pawar, Supriya Angne and Chetashri Bhusari(2020).

This paper[3] propose a course-based recommendation system that use sequential data analysis, such as LSTM, which can capture sequences of information

D. Predictive modeling of student success: An application of data mining methods with an educational web-based system.

The paper[4] explores predictive modeling of student success using data mining methods within an educational web-based system. It's relevant for understanding how data mining can be applied in educational settings.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Data Loading and Preprocessing:

Import the necessary libraries, including pandas for data manipulation and machine learning modules. Load the dataset from a CSV file into a DataFrame using `pd.read_csv`.

Perform one-hot encoding for categorical features, such as 'English', 'Maths', 'Physics', 'Biology', 'Chemistry', 'Accounting', 'Economics', 'Business Studies', 'History', 'Sociology', 'Politics', 'High School CGPA', 'Stream_Point'. Split the dataset into two parts: features (X) and the target variable (y), where X contains all features used for prediction, and y represents the 'Recommended Course' column, which is the target for recommendation.

B. Data Splitting:

Split the data into training and testing sets using `train_test_split`. Allocate 80% of the data for training and 20% for testing.

C. Machine Learning Models Initialization:

Create three base classifiers: XGBoost Classifier, K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) Classifier, and Support Vector Machine (SVM) Classifier.

D. Ensemble Model Creation:

Combine the individual classifiers into an ensemble model using majority voting to make predictions.

E. Training the Ensemble:

Train the ensemble model on the training data using 'fit'.

F. Model Evaluation:

Make predictions on the test data using the ensemble model. Calculate the accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score for model evaluation.

G. User Input for Prediction:

Prompt the user to provide input data for the score factors including 'English', 'Maths', 'Physics', 'Biology', 'Chemistry', 'Accounting', 'Economics', 'Business Studies', 'History', 'Sociology', 'Politics', 'High School CGPA', 'Stream_Point'.

H. Input Data Preparation:

Create input data for prediction as a DataFrame. Encode the input data using the same LabelEncoder used during training for 'Recommended Course' prediction.

I. Making Predictions:

Use the trained ensemble model to predict the recommended course for the input data.

J. Recommendation Display:

Display the recommended courses based on the model's prediction. Provide information on the top five colleges for each recommended course, sorted by NIRF ranking[5] for the year 2023.

Fig.1 Flowchart of the overall process

IV. BUILD MODEL

The course recommendation system utilizes a multi-stage approach to construct a resilient and accurate machine learning model. The process involves importing essential libraries, building the model architecture, and evaluating its performance.

A. Importing Libraries

```
import pandas as pd
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from sklearn.metrics import accuracy_score
import joblib
from sklearn.preprocessing import LabelEncoder
from collections import Counter
import xgboost as xgb
from sklearn.neighbors import KNeighborsClassifier
from sklearn.svm import SVC
import sklearn
```

a) pandas:

Used for versatile data manipulation and preprocessing, pandas serves as a fundamental component of our machine learning pipeline.

b) train_test_split:

Sourced from the scikit-learn library, this function facilitates the division of our dataset into training and testing sets, enabling the evaluation of model performance.

c) accuracy_score:

The main metric for model accuracy, 'accuracy_score' calculates the accuracy of our predictions compared to the ground truth.

d) joblib:

Joblib is an efficient library that helps model storage and sharing. It simplifies the process of managing and deploying machine learning models.

e) LabelEncoder:

LabelEncoder is used to encode target labels into numeric values, ensuring that our machine learning algorithms can work with them correctly.

f) Counter:

This library provides a function to count the occurrences of the list, which is important for the aggregated predictions in our clustering method.

g) xgboost:

XGBoost is used to develop and train the XGBoost classifier, which increases the prediction accuracy of our model.

h) KNeighborsClassifier:

This module supports k-Nearest Neighbors classification, which enables the model to make predictions based on the proximity of data points in feature space.

i) SVC (Support Vector Machine):

The Support Vector Machine classifier is a versatile tool for classification tasks, adding diversity to our ensemble.

B. Building the model

1) Loading the Dataset:

The process starts by importing course data from a CSV file ('courses_new_new.csv') using the pandas library. This data set will serve as the basis for our course recommendation model.

```
df = pd.read_csv('/content/courses_new_new.csv')
college_df = pd.read_csv('/content/Book1.csv')
```

2) Data Preparation:

Divide the data set into a feature matrix (X) and a target variable (y). The feature matrix contains features or columns from the data set, and the target variable represents the recommended courses.

```
X = df[['English', 'Maths', 'Physics', 'Biology', 'Chemistry', 'Accounting', 'Economics', 'Business Studies', 'History', 'Sociology',
        'Politics', 'High School GPA', 'Stream Point']]
y = df['Recommended Course']

label_encoder = LabelEncoder()
y_encoded = label_encoder.fit_transform(y)

X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(X, y_encoded, test_size=0.2, random_state=42)
```

3) Data Splitting:

Split the dataset into training and testing sets, allocating 80% for training and 20% for evaluating the model's performance.

4) Model Initialization and Training:

Save and train the following classifiers.

XGBoost Classifier: Initialize and train the XGBoost classifier on the training data.

K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) Classifier: Initialize the KNN classifier with a traditionally selected number of neighbors (e.g., 3).

Support Vector Machine (SVM) Classifier: Initialize and train SVM classifier with linear kernel.

```
# Create and train XGBoost classifier
xgb_classifier = xgb.XGBClassifier(random_state=42)
xgb_classifier.fit(X_train, y_train)

# Make predictions on the test data using the XGBoost model
y_pred_xgb = xgb_classifier.predict(X_test)

# Create and train K-Nearest Neighbors classifier
knn_classifier = KNeighborsClassifier(n_neighbors=3)
knn_classifier.fit(X_train, y_train)

# Make predictions on the test data using the K-Nearest Neighbors model
y_pred_knn = knn_classifier.predict(X_test)

# Create and train Support Vector Machine classifier
svm_classifier = SVC(kernel='linear', random_state=42)
svm_classifier.fit(X_train, y_train)

# Make predictions on the test data using the Support Vector Machine model
y_pred_svm = svm_classifier.predict(X_test)
```

5) Ensemble Model and Majority Voting

Construct cluster models that combine forecasts from individual classifications through majority voting, a powerful approach to improve overall forecast accuracy. Here's how it works:

Collect predictions from the XGBoost, KNN, and SVM classifiers for each data point in the test set. Calculate the majority opinion, that is, the commonly predicted class of the three distributions for each data point. Create a group prediction list based on the majority of votes.

```
# Create an ensemble model to combine predictions using majority voting
ensemble_predictions = []
for i in range(len(y_test)):
    predictions = [y_pred_xgb[i], y_pred_knn[i], y_pred_svm[i]]
    majority_vote = Counter(predictions).most_common(1)[0][0]
    ensemble_predictions.append(majority_vote)
```

C. User Input:

The model can provide users with specific data for course recommendations. Users enter data points such as 'English', 'Mathematics', 'Physics', 'Biology', 'Chemistry', 'Maths', 'Economics', 'Business Studies', 'History', 'Sociology' and 'Politics', 'HighSchool CGPA' and 'Stream_Point' to get an individual course recommendation

Plus Two Scores Survey

Select Stream:

Commerce Stream Subjects:

Accounting:

Economics:

Business Studies:

English:

Mathematics:

Enter Your Plus Two (12th Grade) CGPA:

D. Prediction and Recommendation

1) Course Recommendation

Using the trained ensemble model, we make predictions based on the user's input data. The model estimates the recommended learning that best matches the quality of the

input.

```
def predict_and_recommend(input_data):
    # Make predictions on the input data using individual classifiers
    new_data_predictions_xgb = xgb_classifier.predict(input_data)
    new_data_predictions_knn = knn_classifier.predict(input_data)
    new_data_predictions_svm = svm_classifier.predict(input_data)

    # Combine the predictions using majority voting for the new data
    predictions = [new_data_predictions_xgb[0], new_data_predictions_knn[0], new_data_predictions_svm[0]]
    top_three = [x[0] for x in Counter(predictions).most_common(3)]

    # Convert the predicted labels back to their original class labels
    predicted_courses = label_encoder.inverse_transform(top_three)

    # Get the top three recommended courses
    recommended_courses = list(predicted_courses)

    # Print recommended courses
    print("Recommended Courses:")
    for course in recommended_courses:
        print(course)
```

2) Filtering Recommended Colleges:

Once we receive the course recommendations, we select and recommend the colleges that offer these courses. We use data from a separate dataset ('Book1.csv') containing college information, including 'NIRF Ranking 2023' and 'Recommended Course'.

3) Sorting Colleges by Ranking:

The recommended colleges are sorted based on the NIRF[5] ranking for each of the recommended courses.

```
# Filter recommended colleges based on the top three predicted courses
recommended_colleges = []

for predicted_course in recommended_courses:
    colleges_for_course = college_df[college_df['Recommended Course'] == predicted_course]
    recommended_colleges.append(colleges_for_course)

# Sort the recommended colleges by NIRF ranking for each course
sorted_recommended_colleges = [colleges.sort_values(by='NIRF_Ranking_2023') for colleges in recommended_colleges]
```

E. Model Evaluation and Accuracy

The performance of the model is evaluated by its ability to recommend relevant courses and colleges based on data. We calculate the accuracy of our model, measuring how well it predicts user-relevant course and college recommendations against ground truth data.

```
accuracy = accuracy_score(y_test, ensemble_predictions)
print(f"Accuracy of the Ensemble model: {accuracy:.2f}")

Accuracy of the Ensemble model: 0.91
```

V. IMPLEMENTATION RESULTS

In this section, we present the implementation and results of the recommendation model. We evaluate its application by presenting an individual course recommendation, a matching college recommendation, and providing a comprehensive equity analysis. The learning proposal model was seamlessly integrated into the web application built using the Django framework. We start the implementation of the model by providing Score analysis to validate the user. The input field invites users to enter the values in the following criteria: 'English', 'Mathematics', 'Physics', 'Biology', 'Chemistry', 'Maths', 'Economics', 'BusinessStudies', 'History', 'Sociology', 'Politics', 'High School CGPA' and 'Stream_Points'. When users submit the form, the model processes the input in real time. Based on the input parameters, the model generates individual course recommendations. Users can see personalized recommendations for high-quality courses.

Recommendations have also been made to colleges regarding recommended courses. Users can also view colleges based on recommended courses.

Recommended Courses	
Finance (B.Com) Accounting (B.Com)	
Top Colleges Available:	
Top 5 Colleges for Finance (B.Com)	
College	NIRF Ranking 2023
Shri Ram College of Commerce (Delhi)	3
Lady Shri Ram College for Women (Delhi)	6
Loyola College (Chennai)	15
St. Xavier's College (Autonomous), Mumbai (Mumbai)	16
Christ University (Bangalore)	19
Top 5 Colleges for Accounting (B.Com)	
College	NIRF Ranking 2023
Shri Ram College of Commerce (Delhi)	3
Lady Shri Ram College for Women (Delhi)	6
Loyola College (Chennai)	15
St. Xavier's College (Autonomous), Mumbai (Mumbai)	16

VI. CONCLUSION

In this study, we developed a practical course recommendation model. It helps students make informed educational choices. Considering subjects such as 'English', 'Maths', 'Physics', 'Biology', 'Chemistry', and others, the model generates individualized career recommendations. What makes the model unique is that it does not stop at courses. It also recommends colleges associated with selected

courses. This two-part program provides comprehensive guidance.

The model performed well in our tests. It provides students with relevant, structured courses and college recommendations. It streamlines the decision-making process and can be a valuable tool for students and teachers.

REFERENCES

- [1] Kore, K., Bobade, A., & Gade, S. (2020). Course Recommendation System Using Machine Learning. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer and Communication Engineering*, 9(3), 7176-7181.
- [2] Rokbani, N., Gargouri, F., & Alimi, A. M. (2018). A Hybrid Approach for Course Recommendation System Based on User and Item Profiles. In *International Conference on Advanced Intelligent Systems and Informatics* (pp. 160-170). Springer.
- [3] Shonal Vaz, Sushama Pawar, Supriya Angne and Chetashri Bhusari(2020). Course Recommendation System using Deep Learning . *International Journal of Advanced Research in Science, Communication and Technology (IJARSCT)* .
- [4] Chen, L., & Bekkerman, R. (2017). Predictive modeling of student success: An application of data mining methods with an educational web-based system. In *International Conference on User Modeling, Adaptation, and Personalization* (pp. 347-352). Springer
- [5] National Institutional Ranking Framework(NIRF) <https://www.nirfindia.org/2023/CollegeRanking.html>
- [6] L. D. Kumalasari and A. Susanto, "Recommendation System of Information Technology Jobs using Collaborative Filtering Method Based on LinkedIn Skills Endorsement." *Sisforma*, vol. 6, 2020.